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Categorisation and evaluation of visualisation practices for communicating uncertain predictions in climate services

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Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge

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Executive summary

In this deliverable we report and reflect on the co-development process and resulting visualisation prototypes of climate service information in the I-CISK Living Lab pilot applications. Following an introduction based on literature and examples of state-of-the-art operational climate services, including examples from Copernicus and other continental and global services, a categorisation of visualisation methods is proposed that constitutes maps, graphs, alerts and aggregated information, uncertainty, and user-centred evaluation. The pilot applications for the seven Living Labs, in Lesotho, Greece, Netherlands, Spain, Italy, Georgia, and Hungary, are analysed for each of the visualisation categories, providing examples of commonly used methods, and of visualisation prototypes that stand-out as co-developed by a particular Living Lab. A reflection is provided on the I-CISK visualisation co-design process and on the resulting visualisation in the pilot climate services.

A key step in the visualisation co-design process, was the preparation of multiple visualisation examples (mock-ups) for each information component for each living-lab (Section 2). These were then used in multi-actor platform workshops and bilateral meetings for feedback, refinement, and selection for implementation. This worked well in the Living Labs, as partly evidenced by the high variability of the look-and-feel of the pilot climate service applications. This is strengthened by the local knowledge on natural hazards, alert levels, challenges, mitigation and adaptation measures, decision processes, user needs and user stories that have found their way in a large part of the display of information in the pilot applications.

All the pilot applications that include hydroclimatic forecasts or climate change projections, also show the uncertainty of these predictions, mostly using forecast plumes and box-plots, in-line with state-of-the-art examples. We found the need for balancing and integrating best practices on the one hand (e.g., to not unintentionally over-state prediction accuracy), and user preferences on the other (e.g., including actual critical event thresholds and requesting localised information at high resolution). This balancing we see as a key success factor from and for human-centred climate services.

For future research and further development of tailored climate services, we recommend to explore the challenges, and use or rather non-use of animated display of hydroclimatic information, which is featured in only a limited number of the I-CISK pilot applications.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Climate services provide platforms for users to easily access and make use of climate information. How information is provided on a climate services platform varies depending on the ultimate target audience's needs and proficiency in interpreting the information. Information is usually presented through a combination of visual aids which may include maps, diagrams, graphs, tables, etc. The choice depends on the specific attributes of the information to be communicated and on user preferences. Central to the I-CISK project, is the co-creation of climate services within the seven Living Labs (LLs) that have been established within the project (WP1). In each of these Living Labs, multi-actor platforms (MAP) have been established, including a wide range of sectors and stakeholders. These have been instrumental in the user-centred co-design of visualisation methods that have been included the (pre-)operational climate services (CSs) that have been piloted within the project.

The locations of the seven Living Labs constitute the upper and middle Guadalquivir basin in Spain, Emilia Romagna in Italy, Rijnland in the Netherlands, Crete in Greece, Budapest in Hungary, Alazani river basin in Georgia, and Southern Lesotho and Senqu Valley in Lesotho. For information about these Living Labs, the users involved, and their climate information needs, we refer to I-CISK Deliverables 1.1. and 2.1. In the remainder of this document we will refer to the Living Labs by the name of the country they are located in.

Developing the co-design process for visualisation of uncertain climate information in the LL pilot applications, has been the responsibility of Task 3.4, which forms a part of Work Package 3 (WP3) of the I-CISK project. This has strong linkages to Task T3.2, which focused on the providing of tailored climate information in these pilot applications, and Task T3.3, which focused on the user-centred evaluation of the information provided. The work in this task progresses and tests part of the co-creation framework that has been developed in the project (in WP2), and has also been in close collaboration with WP5 where the pilot applications have been developed.

1.2 Objectives

The aim of this deliverable is to reflect on the co-design process and the resulting visualisation prototypes that have been developed in the LL pilot applications of climate information, including the representation of uncertainty. Based on literature and state-of-art operational CS examples, mostly providing information at a global or continental scale, a categorisation of visualisation components is used to analyse the I-CISK pilot climate services that have been developed; identify challenges and possibly innovations; and recommend future steps in CS visualisation.

1.3 Document structure

In Section 2 the visualisation co-design and selection process is described, after which Section 3 reports on literature and state-of-the-art examples of operational climate services. Section 4 is the central chapter of this deliverable, reporting on the visualisation of climate information as selected, co-designed, and implemented in the I-CISK LL pilot applications. These results are then reflected upon in Section 5 and the overall conclusions are provided in Section 6.

2 Co-creation process of climate service visualisation prototypes

The procedure to co-create the visualisation prototypes was based on a five-step approach that varies from developing a catalogue of state-of-the-art mock-ups to developing scripts that can allow the operationalisation of the visualisation. In this section we present the procedure (Figure 1). We note that the procedure is generic and is not limited to the type of predictions or projections, i.e. sub-seasonal to seasonal (S2S) predictions or decadal/centennial projections. The five steps are explained below.

Figure 1 The steps followed in WP3 to co-create visualisation prototypes for each Living Lab. Key element of this process is the co-design with users by feedback, refinement, and selection of mock-ups (step 3). Co-creation of the selected visualisation methods will continue in WP5 and WP1 where feedback is being collected from the Living Lab users on the pre-operational pilot applications.

Catalogue of visualisation practices

In this preparatory step, we collected visualisation examples from literature and state-of-the-art climate services and early warning systems. These examples were archived in a Miro board (left-side Figure 2). The examples cover a broad range of visualisation types, including maps, graphs, and aggregated information including alerts.

Setting up user stories

We took note of the user needs (using information from WP1 and WP2) and transformed these needs into story-lines. This process allowed framing the problem, identifying the variables and periods of interest. The user stories served as an input to the developing of the first set of visualisation mock-ups (prototypes).

Co-designing prototypes

In this step we encouraged interactions between scientists, service providers, and local users (via WP1 workshops) in each Living Lab (LL), to co-design a preferred set of visualisation prototypes for the climate service (right-side Figure 2), recognising that the capacity of users differs between LLs as well as within the LL. Starting from the initial set of mock-ups based on the literature and state-of-the-art examples, feedback was collected from the users to inform the co-design process through preferences, selections, and refinements.

Figure 2 The Miro board with the visualisation examples.

Development of the scripts

Following the selection and co-design of the visualisation prototypes, data processing scripts were developed to provide the quantitative elements of the visualisation methods operationally (e.g. to post-process seasonal streamflow forecasts to derive selected percentiles to be displayed in a graph). Different scripts have been generated by WP3 and WP5 partners, tailored to the needs of each LL, establishing a catalogue of scripts that could then be used in the pilot applications.

Delivery of prototypes and scripts

The co-designed prototypes, and data processing scripts, were then implemented in the LL pilot climate service applications (WP5). This goes together with the local knowledge acquired, aiming to translate the generated CS information to support decision-making at the Living Lab scale, e.g. by including user-defined alert thresholds in a forecast graph

Feedback on the pilot applications

The pre-operational pilot applications are being presented to the users in the Living Labs during the last phase of the project for another round of feedback and iteration. At the time of writing of this deliverable, several Living Labs had completed round of co-creation already, while for others it was still ongoing. The state of play we analysed for this deliverable were the on-line pilot applications as they were developed for the second major update of the online pre-operational services, which were released in March-April 2025.

3 Visualisation in literature and state-of-the-art operational climate services

3.1 Literature on visualisation hydroclimatic information and uncertainty

Visualising climate data is crucial for converting information into insights people can actually use. Visualisation of climate services can range from basic line graphs of past temperature trends to detailed, interactive maps that look at seasonal to decade-long climate projections under various greenhouse gas scenarios (Howe et al., 2019). These visualisation methods aim to bridge the gap between complex scientific analysis and user understanding, allowing policy makers, local communities, and researchers to interpret, evaluate, and apply climate data. Carefully designed visualisation can highlight patterns, trends, and anomalies that may otherwise stay unnoticed in the raw data (Tufte, 1983). Choosing colour palettes, chart types, and overall design is crucial in climate data visualisation. For instance, red often signals warmer or above-average conditions, while blue suggests cooler ones. Different shades can help illustrate rainfall intensity (from lighter to darker tones) or emphasize temperature thresholds like freezing points and heatwaves (Bremer et al., 2019). However, these design choices need to fit a wide audience, ranging from expert users looking for scientifically-sound information to non-expert users who can benefit from simpler, more intuitive graphics (van der Linden et al., 2015).

The role of data visualisation in climate services

Climate science involves large, multivariate datasets such as temperature, precipitation, atmospheric pressure, and soil moisture, among other essential climate variables (<https://gcos.wmo.int>). Visualisation and interactive platforms, such as dashboards or web portals, allow users to aggregate such data more understandably (McInerney et al., 2014) and to navigate between different variables, filter by date or geographic region, and display climate scenarios in an accessible manner. A well-designed graph, map, or colour palette can reveal trends in temperature anomalies, precipitation patterns, and storm intensities (Tufte, 1983). At the same time, poor visualisation can mislead decision-makers, e.g. by overstating uncertainty.

Climate services play a vital role for a wide range of decision-makers and industries, such as agriculture, water resource management, infrastructure planning, energy, and public health (Vaughan & Dessai, 2014). Because these services span many sectors, the visualisation techniques these employ should incorporate tailored risk-based perspectives to highlight potential impacts and uncertainties. For instance, colour-coded maps indicating drought or flood-prone regions can guide policy makers in allocating resources. Meanwhile, displaying a sensitivity analysis—like an ensemble spread—helps convey how confident we can be of certain models and projections (Stocker et al., 2013). By illustrating uncertainty through error bars, confidence intervals, or ensemble spreads, end-users can distinguish between highly reliable trends or predictions, and areas that require further data or refinement (Reichler & Kim, 2008).

Climate visualisation should be easy for everyone to understand regardless of their expertise, whether they are climate scientists or non-expert users (Hegarty, 2011). For instance, if visualisation depends on subtle colour changes, clear labels, text annotations, or shape-based cues can be included so viewers that are colour blind can still interpret the data. Summary dashboards could highlight the most important insights and risks to policy makers, while more advanced tools give climate scientists the freedom to dig deeper into the underlying data and modelling details. Ultimately, these methods all share the same foundation: they need to be transparent, easy to understand, and centred on user needs. Adhering to these principles ensures that climate information and alerts are conveyed clearly, paving the way for more informed decisions around preparation, adaptation, and mitigation (Few et al., 2013).

Visualisation for historical climate data

Historical climate data can be derived from multiple sources, such as in-situ observations (e.g. measurements of temperature, precipitation, and wind speed collected via weather stations and ocean buoys), satellite observations (i.e. global coverage data, such as sea surface temperature, land surface temperature, and others, retrieved by remote sensing observations at specific moment in time), proxy data extending our climate record far beyond the period of instrumental observations (e.g. tree ring widths, ice cores, and coral data (Jones et al., 2009)), and reanalysis data produced by assimilating historical observations into global weather models (e.g., ERA5 by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts). Visualisation methods need to merge these various data sources in a coherent narrative, often requiring the alignment of time series, the combination of spatial grids, and the merging of data from different measurement techniques (Blunden & Arndt, 2019). To achieve this, the following non-exhaustive list of graphical techniques can be used:

- Time series plots: One of the most straightforward yet effective ways to show long-term climate data (Tufte, 1983). These capture variations in time, such as annual or monthly temperature anomalies, total rainfall, or other key measurements.
 - Line graphs: A standard representation with the x-axis denoting time (e.g. years) and the y-axis representing the climate variable (temperature, precipitation, etc.).
 - Multi-variate line plots: Multiple lines overlaid on the same chart to compare more than one variable (e.g., temperature versus precipitation) or to show data from various locations side by side.
- Bar-charts: Ideal for highlighting year-to-year changes, outliers, and frequency patterns in climate data. A bar-chart can emphasize fluctuations in total yearly rainfall or show how many days exceeded a particular temperature threshold.
- Histograms for frequency distributions: Histograms show how often specific ranges of values occur, such as certain temperature band or rainfall intensity, helping identify potential trends in extremes (Jézéquel et al., 2018).
- Climate anomaly maps: Show how essential climate variables in certain regions compare to a chosen baseline period, often using colour gradients. For example, global temperature anomaly maps compare each years temperature to a baseline, often visualising warmer-than-average areas in shades of red and cooler regions in blue (Hansen et al., 2010).
- Spatial-temporal animations: Especially useful for illustrating how large-scale climate events develop and dissipate over time (McInerney et al., 2014). For example, a sequence of maps, each representing a different month or season, can visually highlight shifts in sea surface temperature anomalies as they unfold.

For historical climate data, colour palettes typically follow established conventions that facilitate immediate recognition of anomalies. A red-to-blue diverging palette is one of the most common choices for temperature anomalies. Warmer-than-average conditions are shown in shades of red or orange, whereas cooler-than-average conditions are shown in shades of blue (Bremer et al., 2019). Precipitation intensity maps often use a sequential palette from light colours (representing lower rates) to darker ones (representing higher rates). Greens and blues are commonly used for rainfall and wet conditions, while browns or yellows may represent drier conditions. Ensuring the palette is colour-blind-friendly requires careful consideration. Tools like ColorBrewer (Harrower & Brewer, 2003) offer ready-made palettes that can be safely used for various types of data. Colour-blind friendly palettes use carefully chosen hues to maintain contrast. For instance, instead of the classic red-green scale, it is recommended to use a red-blue, orange-purple, or blue-brown diverging scale.

Visualisation of hydroclimatic forecasts and projections

When visualising hydroclimatic forecasts and projections, lead time and uncertainty are added dimensions to consider. For short-term to medium range forecasts (1 to 14 days lead time), for example such as those produced by national meteorological agencies using numerical weather prediction models, visualisation typically includes daily synoptic weather maps highlighting frontal systems, temperature ranges, and precipitation probabilities (Bauer et al., 2015). Sub-seasonal to seasonal (S2S) and seasonal predictions (2 weeks to 7 months lead time) provide a more general outlook, e.g. weekly and monthly expected patterns of temperature and precipitation (Doblas-Reyes et al., 2013), whereas for long-term climate change projections (1 to 100 years), derived from multiple climate models under various greenhouse gas emission scenarios visualisation often shows ensemble means to represent average model responses, along with uncertainty ranges (IPCC, 2021).

Forecasts and predictions come with a number of uncertainties, including i) uncertainty of the initial conditions, ii) internal variability of the climate system, iii) model structure uncertainty (parameterisations, resolution, etc.), and iv) scenario uncertainty (i.e., different emission pathways). Visualizing forecast uncertainty can, for example, be done by:

- Cone of uncertainty, widely used for hurricane tracks, illustrating a central forecast line surrounded by a widening cone to capture less likely but possible deviations (Stephenson & Doblas-Reyes, 2020).
- Box-plots and violin plots, summarizing the distribution of model outputs for a certain variable in a future period (McInerney et al., 2014).
- Ensemble plots, overlaying each model time series (members), a forecast ensemble can highlight the spread of potential outcomes (Kirtman et al., 2013).

For climate change projections, common graphical techniques include:

- Ensemble mean maps: showing the spatial distribution of the mean variation of a certain variable (e.g. temperature) in the future, compared to an historical baseline. Alongside these, standard deviations or confidence intervals may be displayed (IPCC, 2021).
- Multi-panel plots for emission scenarios: visualisation often presents multiple panels side-by-side for different scenarios. This comparison helps stakeholders immediately understand the potential ramifications of different policies regarding greenhouse gas emissions (O'Neill et al., 2016).
- Time slices and snapshots: Instead of continuous animations, many visualisation examples provide discrete snapshots, e.g. mid-century (2036–2065) and late-century (2071–2100). Each snapshot is mapped or graphed for variables like temperature, precipitation, and sea-level rise (Nicholls & Cazenave, 2010).

Colour palettes for forecasts and projections are often similar to those used for historical anomalies to maintain consistency. However, they may include additional colours for extreme warming scenarios. Similar to the historical visualisation colours, it is crucial that these palettes are accessible and interpretable across a wide range of audiences (Bremer et al., 2019). Colours serve multiple purposes in climate visualisation, e.g. communicating magnitude and direction using warmer colours for positive anomalies or increases, cooler colours for negative anomalies or decreases, or highlighting extremes using strongly saturated hues (e.g., heatwaves, extreme rainfall). Different types of palettes have distinct roles. Sequential palettes, transitioning smoothly from light to dark or from low saturation to high saturation, are ideal for display of continuous data, such as precipitation amount or pollution concentration maps. Diverging palettes start with one colour for negative values, transition to a neutral midpoint, and then continue to another colour for positive values, and are commonly used for anomalies, e.g. of temperature. For visualising categorical data qualitative palettes using different colours that do not imply order are more suitable.

The choice of colour can affect how the public perceives climate risks. Some palettes (e.g., bright reds) can sometimes evoke fear or scepticism, while other palettes might understate serious concerns (Corner et al., 2018). Striking a balance between accuracy, emotional resonance, and readability is therefore an integral part of climate visualisation design (Sheppard, 2012). The following are examples of established colour palettes in Climate Services:

- Red-Blue Diverging (for Temperature Anomalies): NASA, NOAA, and the UK Met Office often use such a palette where 0°C anomaly is white or grey, negative anomalies are blue, and positive anomalies are red.
- Brown-Green/Blue (for Precipitation Changes): Drier conditions in brown-yellow hues, wetter conditions in green-blue hues (IPCC, 2021).
- Sunset or Inferno Palettes (for Extreme Heat): Highly saturated reds and blacks used for visualizing extreme heat, especially in the media.

Next to data visualisation, functionalities for user interaction are an integral part of the front-end of operational CS applications, such as tools that allow users to explore how climate conditions in specific regions may change under different scenarios, offering layered map functionalities, time sliders, and the ability to zoom in on local details (IPCC, 2021).

3.2 Visualisation in state-of-the-art operational services

In this section we explore selected examples of state-of-the-art climate services operating at the continental and global scales.

Climate Information explorer

The Climate Information explorer (climateinformation.org) is a climate service developed by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) on behalf of the WMO Green Climate Fund, and has been developed to assess the impact of climate change on climate-dependent sectors. The service visualizes the projected changes to multiple essential climate variables and climate impact indicators (including extremes, i.e. floods and droughts) based on an ensemble of hydro-climatic projections (see Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3 In the Climate Information explorer, users can display maps at gridded or sub-catchment scale with colours indicating the projected percentage change with regard to the present climate for a number of hydroclimatic variables and indicators, selecting from climate projection ensembles, emission scenarios, and future periods (2011-2040, 2041-2070, and 2071-2100).

Both maps and graphs are provided, while regions with unreliable information (i.e. due to lack of consistency from the ensemble of projections) are masked to avoid misinterpretation of the results. In the graphs, uncertainty is communicated through envelopes or box-plots presenting different statistics of the larger ensemble, including, for example, values of the minimum and maximum, median and different percentiles.

Reference: <https://climateinformation.org> (date: 2025-04-20)

Figure 4 In the Climate Information explorer, users can select a grid cell on the map, for which a graph or table with the climate change projection data can be displayed and downloaded, as can be done with the underlying data. The graphs present box-plots with a varying level of detail; high for 30-year average (lower panel), and lower for monthly means (upper panel). Links to background, metadata and explanatory information are provided, as are links to key external websites.

Global hydrometeorological seasonal forecasts

As an example of a climate service providing seasonal forecasts, the global CS based on SMHI’s World-wide HYPE hydrological model (WWH), provides state-of-the-art visualisation (Figure 5 and Figure 6). With the skill of seasonal forecasts of hydrometeorological variables that are displayed in the service varying both spatially

and as a function of lead time, regions with no skill can be masked (not displayed) accordingly. The focus of such seasonal forecasting services is to provide information on above/near/below normal conditions (classes defined by the terciles) or above/below the high/low extreme conditions respectively (classes defined by the 90th and 10th percentiles). With the colour itself indicating a specific condition being forecast for a specific region, the density of the colour indicates the confidence of this condition being met. Here confidence is defined by the probability of the values in the forecast ensemble exceeding a defined threshold. Besides maps, graphs are also presented where the hydro-climatic conditions of a region are predicted for some months ahead and the probabilistic results are visualized with box-plots (which provide summary statistics of the large ensemble such as min-max, median and 25th and 75th percentiles). Moreover, monthly dependent thresholds are also depicted to represent the different conditions (above/near/below and extremes), with this assisting in decision-making.

Figure 5 The SMHI Hypeweb climate service visualizes seasonal hydrometeorological forecasts with multiple icons showing where background information can be retrieved, including also an option to mask regions for which the forecasts (for the selected variable and lead time) have no skill. The colour legend shows that the seasonal forecasts of monthly means are presented as above, near or below normal conditions (model climatology), with high, medium or low probability (calculated from the forecast ensemble).

Figure 6 Seasonal hydrological forecasts based on SMHI’s Word-wide HYPE model with a map to select a region for which forecasts (box-plots for each lead month) of a hydrometeorological variable are visualized on a graph at the bottom. Forecast data can be downloaded if required.

Apart from future projections and seasonal forecasts, climate services can also provide information and data on the historical conditions and monitoring statuses of the regions of interest. The SMHI Hypeweb service visualizes as maps the long-term means of multiple hydro-climatic variables, while graphs are presented for a specific region and every historical year (Figure 7 and Figure 8). The latter graphs also present as a background the past climatology so that users can have an improved understanding of the conditions observed for the year of interest with respect to past records.

Figure 7 SMHI’s service over Europe displays a map for historic mean simulated data at the sub-catchment resolution for a number of hydro-meteorological variables. These variables can be selected from a drop-down list. Opacity slides are used to visualise country borders and catchment outlines.

Figure 8 SMHI's service over Europe visualizes the upstream area of the region of interest, while a map displays the historical simulations including past climatology for comparison. This is available for a number of hydro-meteorological variables selectable through the drop-down list. A download and an information button are provided.

Copernicus Emergency Management Services

As a part of the Copernicus Emergency Management Services (CEMS, emergency.copernicus.eu), the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) and European Drought Observatory (EDO) provide information on hydroclimatic variables and natural hazard indicators that are closely related to the I-CISK Living Labs that incorporate seasonal forecasts for early preparedness.

EFAS uses an inter-active map as the central display of its services (Figure 9). River stations for which there is a probability of high flows in the observations or forecasts are indicated with a colour-coded square, with yellow, red, and purple representing forecasts exceeding the 2, 5, or 20-year return period flow. Symbols are used to make the user aware of other information to be displayed, such as latest observations for both meteorology and hydrology, climatology, and forecast quality. By clicking a river section, station, or reporting point on the map, more detailed information for that location is displayed in multiple graphs and tables, such as the streamflow time series graph of Figure 10. The time series graph uses the same alert colours in the back ground, includes recent observations, deterministic streamflow forecasts and ensemble based probabilistic forecasts. Forecast uncertainty is represented with box-plots derived from the ensemble forecast.

Figure 9 CEMS European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) map display providing rapid awareness of river locations in Europe where probabilistic forecasts exceed flood pre-alert thresholds.

Figure 10 CEMS European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) pop-up forecast graph when selecting a river location. The uncertainty information derived from ensemble hydrometeorological forecasts is displayed through box-plots.

Forecast quality can be visualised by colouring river stations depending on the evaluated skill (Figure 11). An intensity colour pallet is used, with light intensity showing low forecast skill and high intensity for high performance. Clicking on a station displays graphs of forecast skill against lead time (Figure 12).

Figure 11 CEMS European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) visualises forecast quality information with coloured dots for each evaluated river location.

Figure 12 CEMS European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) pop-up graphs for forecast quality information for different lead times.

The European Drought Observatory (EDO) displays current drought conditions on a map (Figure 13), with a limited set of three colours yellow, orange, and red, to indicate the level of pre-alert from low to high (Watch, Warning, Alert). A range of drought indicators and hydroclimatic variables, observed and forecast, can be selected for display on the map. By clicking on a location on the map, a bar-chart displays the time series of the selected information with a 10-day interval (Figure 14).

Figure 13 CEMS European Drought Observatory (EDO) displays current drought situation over Europe, e.g. with the combined drought indicator expressing pre-alerts of three different levels from watch to alert, on a coloured gridded map in which detailed information can be derived from each grid-cell.

Figure 14 CEMS European Drought Observatory (EDO) enables users to show bar-charts of recent and present time series of the selected drought indicator

Seasonal drought forecasts can be displayed on the map as well, though at a coarser resolution, which reflects the atmospheric models used. An classification of the anomaly (drier or wetter compared to climatology) rather than pre-alerts, is used to indicate the higher level of uncertainty associated with the forecasts (Figure 15).

Figure 15 CEMS European Drought Observatory (EDO) seasonal drought forecasts over Europe, displaying a course resolution gridded colour map, indicating driest to wettest predicted conditions relative to climatology for a 3-month lead time. Using the drop-down menu, other hydroclimatic variables, drought indicators, and lead times can be selected.

4 Co-developed visualisation in Living Lab pilot climate services

In this section we report on the climate service (CS) visualisation prototypes selected and co-developed with the Living Lab multi-actor platforms as implemented in the I-CISK pilot CS applications. The screenshots and analysis presented reflect the status of March and April 2025. Further updates to the applications may occur following user feedback up to the end of the I-CISK project, or beyond where services are continued after October 2025. Using the literature and operational CS examples described in the previous section, we analyse the co-developed visualisation methods that have been implemented in the I-CISK pilot applications. This analysis uses the following categorisation: maps, graphs, aggregated information (including alerts), uncertainty, and quality (forecast performance). The final sub-section presents methods used to navigate the application and select layers to be displayed.

The aim of this section is to analyse and discuss the range of visualisation practices that are used, and not to provide an exhaustive replication of the on-line pilot applications (i-cisk.dev.52north.org/living-labs/). For each visualisation category we identify the methods that are used most, and provide representative examples with screenshots, as well as examples of visualisation practices that are unique from individual Living Labs.

4.1 Maps

All Living Lab pilot CS applications use maps for visualisation, and the majority has a map as the central means of display. The level of detail of information displayed on the map, and level of inter-activity differs among the applications. As an example, the Living Lab in Georgia displays a map of the area to indicate location and allow selection of hydrological stations at which seasonal forecasts can then be displayed. Sub-catchments are also displayed but are not selectable and are for information only. There are no hydrometeorological variables or alerts displayed on the map. The format and colours of the map are chosen such that the stations stand out and are easy to select. For the selected station seasonal streamflow predictions can be displayed (Figure 16).

Figure 16 The pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Georgia uses a map to select river stations for display of seasonal streamflow predictions

The Living Lab in Greece displays a map with layers of historic, forecast, or projected hydroclimatic variables and derived impact indicators. Clicking on any point on the map brings up the current climate information and a graph with projected climate with an uncertainty band. The map combines a standard topographical look with high resolution coloured grid overlay (Figure 17). The diverging colour palette with blue, green/yellow, and red can be further optimised for colour-blind users.

Figure 17 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Greece, with a high-resolution coloured map as the central visualisation tool. Multiple layers can be selected, and for any grid-cell on the map, pop-up information and time series graphs can be displayed.

The Living Lab in Spain displays seasonal predictions of precipitation and temperature on gridded maps, with the option to display a graph for the selected 230 m grid-cell (Figure 18). The information is displayed at a monthly time step. This is in-line with the best practice recommendation from literature to display forecasts at a lower time resolution when the lead time increases, e.g. a monthly rather than a daily time step for seasonal lead times to match the lower forecast skill at longer lead times.

Figure 18 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Spain, with visualisation of seasonal forecasts on isoline coloured maps with pre-alert information

Climate change projections are mostly displayed at a coarser resolution than the observations and seasonal forecasts, which is in-line with literature. The Living Lab in Spain, for example, displays climate projection information on course gridded maps (rather than the higher resolution smooth isoline maps used for seasonal forecasts) with selection button on top to select which information to display. The time resolution presented, with a slide-bar for selecting the year and season in the future to be displayed (Figure 19), is higher than in the example state-of-the-art operational CS (Section 3) where projections are presented averaged for 30-year periods. This component of the pilot application is still under development.

- Dic, Ene, Feb (invierno)
- Mar, Abr, May (primavera)
- Jun, Jul, Ago (verano)
- Sep, Oct, Nov (otoño)

Figure 19 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Spain, with a display of climate change projected impact on drought indicators such as number of consecutive days without precipitation.

The Living Lab in Hungary, on urban heat islands, also makes extensive use of mapping (Figure 20). For ease of interpretation, a simple map view has been implemented, using colour-coded circles (green/yellow/red) to indicate normal, caution, and danger heat levels. Additionally, automated alerts have been integrated—for instance, neighbourhoods are highlighted in purple if the heat index exceeds a critical threshold for more than an hour, signalling an extreme heat event.

Figure 20 The pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Hungary uses maps to display urban heat-island measurements and model predictions

Some of the pilot CS applications in the Living Labs include maps that provide more detailed user-specific background information, such as the hydrogeological catchment as based on local knowledge and land use characteristics information provided for a sub-catchment, such as in the case of the Living Lab in Spain (Figure 21). Inclusion of such detailed background information is recognised as a user-request, as is the combining of multiple information services in one so as not to have to switch between multiple applications. This request was also mentioned by users in the Living Lab in the Netherlands, and has been implemented as far as possible within the time-frame of the project (e.g. status of drought mitigation measures, forecast alerts, and climate change impact information are combined in one pilot application).

Figure 21 Detailed, high resolution, static background information based on local knowledge of the case study area as displayed for (parts of) the Living Lab in Spain.

Lastly, for historic information the Living Lab in Spain stands-out by having developed a map with sliding mask function to compare hydrometeorological variables and derived drought indices by month (Figure 22) from selected historic years. This is a nice inter-active and intuitive feature that invites dynamic interaction from the visiting user. The diverging colour palette from red to blue, is well chosen for colour-blind accessibility.

Figure 22 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Spain, with an innovative map with sliding mask to compare hydroclimatic information and derived indices for two different points in time.

4.2 Graphs

Time series graphs are used in almost all pilot applications, though these are mostly not the central (landing page) visualisation. The Living Lab pilot CS applications use a wide range of mostly standard graph types. Some of the time series graph types have already been presented as a pop-up option when clicking on a location on the maps (Figure 16 and Figure 17). The pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Georgia, for example, displays streamflow time series of five different types, from which the user can select what they would like to display. This includes two types of box-plots showing streamflow data aggregated by month, or as an accumulation over three months. This was specifically requested by users as a key indicator in their decision processes. The graphs also display alert thresholds for low streamflow. Forecasts and the latest observations are shown next to each other in one graph (Figure 16). The pilot application of the Living Lab in Italy features the same display, visualisation, and options, as the users of the LLs in Georgia and Italy have similar needs.

The Living Lab in Greece serves as an example of commonly used time series with an uncertainty band based on ensemble forecasts (Figure 17). These types of graphs will also be discussed in the section below on uncertainty information (Section 4.4).

The Living Lab in Spain uses bar-charts for displaying historic and climate change projections of meteorological variables and derived drought indices (Figure 23). The graph is displayed for the location (grid-cell) selected on a map.

Figure 23 Examples of commonly used types of time series graphs, from the pilot CS application of the Living Lab in Spain.

4.3 Alert and aggregated information

Complex technical hydroclimatic information can be aggregated to actionable indicators or alerts for one or more user groups. Some user groups (sectors) may be interested only in such aggregated information, while others would like to have the option to display further, more detailed, information on demand.

The pilot CS for Lesotho, for example, is strongly focussed on alert and impact information to support the early action protocols that form the main decision processes supported by the service. Maps are used to indicate whether and in which district there is a current hydrometeorological alert, and how many people are potentially affected (inhabitants of the district). The set of visualisation examples, therefore, does not include graphs with forecast information. The lead time at which these alerts are displayed is indicated, at monthly time steps, on top of the window through buttons that can be selected (Figure 24).

Figure 24 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Lesotho, aggregating hydroclimatic information on cold waves and droughts displayed with a colour ramp to indicate the population that is potentially exposed at district level.

For sector-specific indicators, the Living Lab in Greece has opted for a textual descriptive terminology indicated with a legend and colour scale on the map (Figure 25), with the option to display the graph with seasonal prediction of the index (by clicking on the map). The seasonal prediction map can be animated using a two-week time step.

Figure 25 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Greece, showing aggregated information of sector-specific impact indicators, in this case on hydroclimate state for tourism.

Other visualisation option used for alerts is to provide a calendar view with the forecast weeks and months displayed with a status colour (green for 'all good', to red for 'high alert'). This is as used in the Living Lab in the Netherlands. This allows the user to click on a week of interest and view brief textual information on the reason for the alert and an option to obtain more detailed forecast information in maps and graphs by clicking on the button (Figure 26).

Figure 26 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in the Netherlands, with user-specific aggregated coloured and textual alert information for droughts.

Awareness-raising visuals also typically display aggregated information. Particularly the Living Lab in Hungary focusses on awareness raising. Beyond the direct analysis of urban heat data, a wide range of visualisation and outreach tools have been deployed to help communities understand and adapt to extreme heat. First, three short educational videos about urban heat and its impacts were produced and shared on Facebook and other on-line platforms. These videos provide straightforward explanations of how heat waves form, how they affect daily life, and what individuals can do to stay safe. In parallel, a large roll-up banner has been designed to promote the climate service itself at public events and conferences, offering a concise but eye-catching introduction to its goals and benefits.

The visualisation methods of the Living Lab in Hungary follow a user-specific approach. Using a variety of visualisation techniques not only brings urban heat data to life, it also makes it more accessible and actionable for diverse stakeholders. For policy makers and urban planners, static heat maps can quickly highlight critical hotspots and justify interventions, while interactive GIS platforms allow them to test scenarios (e.g., green roofs, tree planting) and see projected cooling benefits. Citizens benefit from real-time dashboards to stay informed on the occurrence of dangerous temperatures in their neighbourhood, particularly during extreme heat events. These dashboards also allow them to learn about simple adaptation strategies. Meanwhile, health authorities can identify areas where vulnerable populations overlap with temperature extremes, and then tailor public health advisories or emergency responses. Researchers gain advanced insights from detailed 3D models and heat vulnerability indexes, enabling them to study micro-climate phenomena in depth and experiment with predictive models. Finally, community organizations can use easy-to-understand visuals (Figure 27), such as puzzle visuals for children or short documentary films. These allow engaging with various age groups, encouraging climate literacy, and rallying support for collective adaptation measures.

Figure 27 For younger audiences, the Living Lab in Hungary features both a puzzle visual where children piece together the thermal image of an elephant, and classroom-focused demonstrations (pictured) that let students experiment with heat cameras, sparking interest in citizen science from an early age.

By combining thermal drone surveys, interactive web mapping, real-time sensor dashboards, 3D city renderings, and user-focused creative media, the climate service ensures that urban heat data is presented

in multiple formats, each suited to a particular goal or audience. Whether it is comparing shaded parks and asphalt lots on a static heat map, drilling down into block-level temperatures via an interactive tool, or exploring the human dimension through a Heat Vulnerability Index, each visualisation method bridges the gap between complex climate data and everyday decision-making. This approach broadens participation and drives a deeper understanding of how extreme heat can be tackled at local and citywide scales.

4.4 Display of information on uncertainty

For displaying of information about the uncertainty in (seasonal) forecast and climate projections, a variety of state-of-the-art visualisation methods from ensemble prediction methods have been selected in the pilot CS applications. Plumes and box-plots are the most widely used to visualise uncertainty. These are derived from selected percentiles obtained from the forecast ensemble.

For seasonal streamflow predictions (sub-catchment outlet), at weekly time step, the Living Lab in Greece uses ensemble-based probabilistic forecast presented with box-plots (Figure 28).

Figure 28 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Greece, displaying seasonal ensemble streamflow forecasts with box-plots on a time series graph.

For climate information in the CS for the Living Lab in Greece, uncertainty is displayed by a band that has been derived from the complete range of projections. The uncertainty band can be selected or unselected by the user of the application. The user can also select the time horizon from either the standard climate outlook periods of mid and end century, or displaying the information per decade (Figure 17). The CS in the Living Labs in Italy and Georgia use more detailed plumes for seasonal forecasts, containing multiple colour shades based on 11 percentiles (Figure 29).

Figure 29 Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Italy, with seasonal forecast information displayed for selected stations as a plume detailed with colour-shades for multiple bandwidths based on percentiles.

Figure 30 The Pilot CS application from the Living Lab in the Netherlands displays 2-months lead time of a seasonal forecast with a plume containing two shades based on percentiles, in combination with user-defined thresholds.

The CS application from the Living Lab in the Netherlands, shows the seasonal ensemble forecasts with a plume of five percentiles (Figure 30). Selected user pre-alert thresholds are indicated. The data is displayed continuously at the original daily step of the underlying data (e.g. not aggregated per week or month) and as absolute values. Displaying user-defined alert levels against forecast values, rather than, for example, forecast deviations from model climatology (anomalies), may (inadvertently) suggest more accuracy than the seasonal forecasts can provide, even though the uncertainty band of the ensemble forecast is shown.

The pilot applications of the Living Labs in Georgia and Italy have multiple options for display of prediction uncertainty from which the user can select by drop-down menu, as presented in the beginning of this chapter. These are shown as pop-ups from its central map (Figure 16) and discussed in Section 4.2 on graphs.

4.5 User-centred evaluation

Results for the evaluation of the quality of hydroclimatic information (forecasts and projections) and derived impact indicators for the Living Lab CSs are available as off-line information, putting evaluation results into user-centred thresholds. The Living Lab in Spain, for example, has analysed and found variability in skill for different regions within the case study area. Showing evaluation results on-line of user-centred performance assessment methods and metrics is a next step that can be introduced in the CS.

Visualising uncertainty information in a climate service, as described above, conveys the level of confidence that a user can assign to its predictions, but a user may still be unclear about how to use the information when making decisions. Decisions are typically made using thresholds, for example the river discharge associated with out of bank flow i.e. flooding, and identifying when the climate service predicts the threshold to be crossed. Therefore, it is useful to evaluate the ability of a climate service to predict the crossing of these decision-making thresholds. In I-CISK this evaluation has been done using a contingency-table based approach, where the predicted crossing of a threshold is compared against the observed crossing of that threshold. This allows the number of hits (when a threshold is correctly predicted), misses and false alarms to be recorded. For probabilistic predictions, the evaluation was done for different levels of forecast probability of the threshold being exceeded. The recorded hits, misses and false alarms are then used to compute a skill score, such as the Threat score, which can show the accuracy of the climate service in predicting threshold crossing events.

Results from this type of user driven evaluation were presented as heat maps, which showed the Threat score obtained at different lead times and different levels of probability of exceeding the threshold. These allow a user to quickly identify the optimum forecast probability for triggering alerts of exceeding the threshold, at each lead time. In the example below (Figure 31), a user would obtain the optimal performance when using a forecast probability of at least 10% for triggering alerts at all lead times.

Figure 31 Example of a heat map showing the Threat score computed by applying different levels of forecast probability of yellow status low flow conditions for the Living Lab in Italy.

Whilst the Threat score summarises the hits, misses and false alarms into a single score of accuracy, many users expressed a desire to also visualise these three components to provide context to the score. This context is required because users need to balance the risk of false alarms against the risk of missed events

when making a decision, and the Threat score alone does not provide this context. The example above (Figure 31) identified requiring a 10% forecast probability as the optimum to trigger alerts, but plotting the associated hits, misses and false alarms (Figure 32) shows a large occurrence of missed events. This provides information to the user that there is still a high risk of missed events if they were to use this 10% forecast probability requirement within their decision making. A higher probability threshold would reduce the number of missed events, but would equally increase the number of false alarms.

Figure 32 Example of the hits, misses and false alarm counts computed by applying a 10% predicted crossing probability threshold to predict the occurrence of yellow status low flow conditions for the Living Lab in Italy.

The results of user driven evaluation are often presented to users through reports and meetings, and are accompanied with clear guidance on how to use the climate services within their decision making. However, the results are often not integrated directly into the visualisation of the climate service itself. For example, if a user-based evaluation identifies an optimum forecast threshold crossing probability associated with making a particular decision, the visualisation of the climate service could be adjusted to highlight when this threshold is predicted to be crossed. This would convey to the user that the climate service is forecasting conditions associated with the making a particular decision. Future work could investigate adapting the visualisation of climate services to integrate the findings from user-based evaluation more explicitly.

4.6 Functionalities for users

Navigation between different CS components within the pilot application is an important aspect for user experience, and starts with the landing page. The landing pages follow three different approaches among the Living Labs, starting with 1) a map with stations (hydrometeorological data focus), 2) Status indicator (alert focus), and 3) Information overview (context focus).

The map and alert status examples (from the Living Labs in Italy and the Netherlands) have been presented above, but the landing-page with focus on project information, of the Living Lab in Spain, we include here. The information overview of the landing page of the pilot application, Figure 33, highlights that it has been developed as part of an EU research project product, and its main purpose is to provide climate information on droughts for different time scales. The available service components are displayed on top, ranging from historic, to seasonal forecast, to climate projection impact information.

Figure 33 Landing page of the pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Spain with project information and main objective

Most LL pilot applications have chosen for the selection of information to be displayed to be done through drop-down menus. Information icons are provided with a pop-up to allow meta-data and potentially static uncertainty or performance information to be added, as well as guidance on the selection for display options (Figure 34).

Figure 34 Pop-up text boxes (upper panel) and navigation by drop-down menus of the pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Greece (lower panel)

Feedback received on the visualisation preferences sometimes differed among members of the multi-actor platform in one Living Lab. In these cases majority choice often had to be made, although for some elements a user-customised functionality was developed. Users of the LL in the Netherlands, for example, can select a sectoral user group and through doing so de-select some of the hydroclimatic information displayed, and receive sector-specific pre-alert information (Figure 26).

Lastly, we provide an example of visualisation practices that have been designed to support navigation. A good example is implemented in the LL in Greece. This application indicates the time domain presently on-screen with a graphical overview as in Figure 35. Although this does not present any information on uncertainty, it elegantly triggers the user's awareness of the time-frame one is currently looking at, which helps to manage expectations, including expectations on the uncertainty of the information provided.

Figure 35 Visual representation of currently displayed time domain in the pilot CS application from the Living Lab in Greece.

5 Reflection

From the overview of visualisation methods implemented in the pilot applications, we first draw general conclusions per visualisation category. In subsequent sections, we further reflect on the co-design process, the visualisation of uncertain predictions, and the position of I-CISK visualisation with respect to state-of-the-art.

5.1 Visualisation categories

From the overview presented in Section 4 of the visualisation methods used in the I-CISK Living Lab pilot applications, the 'map' stands out as the most widely used visualisation method (Table 1). Maps have been implemented in each of the seven Living Lab pilot applications (i-cisk.dev.52north.org). We can conclude that in today's user-centred climate services, an interactive map with at least the functionality for a sectoral user to zoom-in to and recognise her or his area of interest, e.g. catchment, district, agricultural field, etc., is a minimum requirement. This is in tune with the state-of-the-art operational climate service examples presented in Section 3.2.

With respect to colour palettes, some of the I-CISK Living Lab maps (Section 4) show palettes that match existing local information services, but can be further optimised for colour-blind accessibility. This points at an interesting balance or choice to be made in the climate service co-creation process: balancing between on the one hand fitting-in with existing systems for uniformity and recognisability by the users, to ease the uptake of the new climate service, and on the other hand bringing in changes of visualisation intended to improve the climate service usability in the long run.

Next to maps, graphs are displayed in almost all Living Lab pilot applications. Only in the pilot application for Lesotho graphs are not used (grey-filled cell in Graphs column of Table 1), which is explained by the strong focus of the CS in Lesotho on disaster risk alerts.

Aggregated and alert information is used in some, but not all Living Lab pilot applications (Table 1). This may well align with the intended use and user groups of the climate service. For user groups with technical background in fields related to hydroclimatic information, such as water resource management, focus on the predicted hydroclimatic variables or anomalies from climatic mean of such variables, may be the main requirement. For sectoral users on the other hand (e.g. tourism, agriculture, etc.) main interest may be in derived indices or alerts for their sector. An additional reason for not displaying user-centred aggregated information such as alerts is that in some Living Labs, alert levels for early awareness of upcoming impactful events (e.g. droughts or floods) have not yet been established by the local user groups.

A positive finding is that information on uncertainty of hydroclimatic predictions is visualised for each of the Living Lab climate services that display hydroclimatic seasonal forecasts or projections (five of the seven Living Labs, Table 1). Time series plumes composed of percentile uncertainty bandwidth (e.g. 10-90th percentile) are used most, followed by box-plots to display prediction uncertainty for monthly, yearly, or 30-year average values.

In addition to the visualisation categories discussed here, the Living Lab in Greece included in their pilot application the option to play an animation of climate model output maps for a sequence of years, and the Living Lab in Hungary developed videos and games focussed on awareness raising.

Table 1 Summary table of visualisation methods used in each of the seven I-CISK Living Labs (Grey fill indicates 'not included, text in italics indicate examples of specific type of visualisation presented)

Living Lab country and sectors involved	Main theme of the climate service pilot application	Maps	Graphs	Aggregated information and Alerts	Uncertainty information	Other
Georgia Water resource management Hydropower, Agriculture	Water Resource Management Service	<i>Topographic map to select points of interest</i>	<i>Time series line graphs</i>		<i>Box-plots and plumes of percentile bands</i>	
Greece Tourism Water resource management, Transport, Infrastructure, Accommodation	Cross-Sector Planning Service for Tourism	<i>Climatic variable and indicator values</i>	<i>Time series line graphs</i>	<i>Sectoral hydroclimatic suitability indicators</i>	<i>Box-plots on line graph</i>	<i>Animated maps</i>
Hungary Urban Planning Health, Tourism	Urban Heat Planning Service	<i>Climatic variable values</i>	<i>Time series line graphs</i>			<i>Awareness raising images, videos, and games</i>
Italy Water management Agriculture, Industry, Energy, Environmental management, Utilities	Water Resource Management Service	<i>Topographic map to select points of interest</i>	<i>Time series line graphs</i>		<i>Box-plots and plumes of percentile bands</i>	
Lesotho Disaster Risk Reduction Anticipatory Action Humanitarian aid Government, Agriculture	Impact Based Forecasting Service	<i>Alert status</i>		<i>Alert status (on/off) for natural hazards</i>		
Netherlands Water management, water tourism, Agriculture	Drought Awareness Service	<i>Climatic indicator values</i>	<i>Time series line graphs</i>	<i>Alert level for natural hazards</i>	<i>Plumes of percentile bands</i>	
Spain Agriculture, Livestock Forestry	Climate Planning Service	<i>Climatic variable and indicator values</i>	<i>Bar charts</i>	<i>Sectoral hydroclimatic indicators</i>	<i>Plumes of percentile bands</i>	

5.2 Co-design process

From the visualisation examples presented in Section 4, it can be seen that there is strong variability among the pilot climate service applications of the seven I-CISK Living Labs, which indicates a strong influence of each of the Living Lab multi-actor platforms with a unique composition of sector representatives and their user requirements. In cases where there are similarities, this concerns Living Labs with partly common types of users and objectives, such as water resources managers in the Living Labs of Georgia and Italy that both have a clear interest in seasonal availability of water. Overall, the many differences between the pilot applications, rather than uniformity, can be seen as an indication that the co-design process for visualisation has been successful. The approach to prepare mock-up presentations with a range of visualisation options for the multi-actor platform (MAP) members to indicate their preferences, has successfully contributed to these highly customised hence different applications. This is strengthened by the local knowledge on natural hazards, alert levels, challenges, mitigation and adaptation measures and decision processes, and the user needs (user stories) derived from those by the MAP members, that have found their way in a large part of the selection and visualisation of information in the pilot applications.

5.3 Visualisation of uncertainty

From the hydroclimatic prediction examples presented in Section 4, we see as a positive result that uncertainty is being presented in all pilot applications that present seasonal predictions and climate change projections. When reflecting on the details of how these represent uncertainty and best-practice recommendations from operational systems and literature (Section 3), we like to highlight some differences, both for presenting climate change (impact) information and for seasonal forecasts.

For presenting climate change and impact information, best-practice recommendations from climate sciences do not always match with needs expressed by sectoral users in I-CISK Living Labs (e.g. water tourism and agriculture). State-of-the-art climate projection information is often presented as 30-year period average to account for uncertainty, whereas sectoral users in the Living Labs (e.g. in the Netherlands and Spain) expressed the need for information over the next five to ten years. This time scale is important for strategic investment planning by these sectoral users.

For the seasonal forecasts, in some of the Living Lab pilot applications, we see time series graphs with a daily time step uncertainty bands of actual forecast levels and volumes of the hydroclimatic variables, along with user-defined alert thresholds. Best practices for seasonal hydroclimatic forecasts, however, suggest only displaying monthly box-plots of anomalies from model climatology (not from thresholds based on actual observations) because of the high degree of uncertainty at seasonal lead times.

Both examples indicate the need for balancing and integrating best practices from hydroclimatic sciences on the one hand, and sectoral user preferences and interpretability on the other. This balancing we see as a key success factor of the user driven design of human-centred climate services.

5.4 State-of-the-art

When comparing the visualisation examples of I-CISK pilot applications in Section 4 with operational climate services of Section 3, we conclude that the visualisation methods used in the Living Labs generally match state-of-the-art standard. However, the co-design in the individual Living Labs has also indicated directions for innovation. These include intuitive visualisation of which time horizon is presently on screen in the pilot application of the Living Lab in Greece, and a dynamic map (slider) to interactively display hydroclimatic differences and similarities from one year to another in the pilot application of the Living Lab in Spain. A third innovation concerns the approach to more clearly visualise the availability within the same application of climate change information next to the seasonal predictions, e.g. in the Living Lab in the Netherlands, aiming to attract users to the long-term information as well, and foster awareness and discussion on adaptation strategies.

Multi-panel plots, used in literature for displaying multiple climate change information, e.g. multiple projections from different scenarios and climate models, have not been included in the pilot CS applications. This may well be because these are considered too technical by most sectoral end users, and too small on (mobile phone) displays without the option to zoom-in an area of interest as with single maps.

Only one of the pilot CS applications includes animations displaying a time sequence of maps (LL in Greece), whereas these have been identified in literature as suitable means of illustrating trends in historic hydroclimatic data and expected changes in climate change projections. Animated maps thus remain a potential direction for further innovation of visualisation practices in co-designed climate services.

6 Conclusions

In this document we have categorised and evaluated the visualisation methods as implemented in the pilot climate service applications of each of the seven I-CISK Living Labs; in Lesotho, Greece, Netherlands, Spain, Italy, Georgia, and Hungary. All of the pilot applications that display hydroclimatic forecasts or projections, adopted state-of-the-art methods to visualise uncertainty, mostly concerning forecast plumes of uncertainty bands and box-plots.

When evaluating the co-design process, the strong variability among the pilot CS applications developed shows that the process was successful, resulting in user-centred visualisation tailored to the needs of the diverse users that were engaged in the process.

This reflection on climate service visualisation also showed that the user-centred approach, aiming to integrate user preferences and local knowledge in the visualisation of hydroclimatic data as much as possible, sometimes needs to balance requirements and preferences of users, with best-practice recommendations from climate and forecasting sciences.

Promising innovations concern an attractive and interactive comparison of hydroclimatology between different years, e.g. for visualising climate change impact, and combining short-term seasonal forecasting for event management with long term impact projections for climate change adaptation in one application. An intuitive visualisation of which time horizon is presently on screen supports such multi-time domain climate services.

For future climate service development in general, we recommend exploring the challenges, and the use, or rather non-use of animated display of hydroclimatic information, as these currently feature only limited in the I-CISK pilot applications.

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Appendix 1 Glossary

Acronym	Definition
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CS	Climate Service
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LL	Living Lab
S2S	Sub-seasonal to Seasonal
WMO	World Meteorological Organization

I-CISK

HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

Colophon:

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